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THE SCIENCE OF JUDICIAL PRECEDENTS AND THE CHAMELEONIC NATURE OF JUDICIAL DECISIONS IN POLITICAL MATTERS IN NIGERIA

By

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ABSTRACT

The judiciary is the major pillar in the tripod that erects modern democratic governments. It creates a check and balance on the other two arms whipping them into line wherever and whenever they err. Through the interpretation and application of laws to facts and circumstances which must be such that it produces a scenario of near mathematical accuracy and predictability. The decisions coming from the courts are based on fixed principles that are tested and verifiable. However, since the return of democracy in 1999, the judiciary has been inconsistent in giving out decisions that are irreconcilably dialectical to each other. This has made the once hallowed institution an object of scorn. This is largely due to manipulations of well-known established principles of law principally to satisfy pecuniary interest. This paper examines this changing faces of judicial decisions in political matters and recommends that the judiciary must have to recover from this virus that is fast destroying the system for a stable political system. This paper adopts a doctrinal approach as only statutes, judicial decisions and other secondary sources will be used in arriving at conclusions. It has been observed that: corruption and the nature of appointments into judicial offices is the major factor that has occasioned this changing nature of decisions coming from our courts. It is recommended that the anti-corruption agencies should beam their searchlight more on the judiciary in order to fish out bad eggs. Again, the nature and character of appointment which is more of inheritance should be jettisoned so that the judiciary will have the best brains who are independent in their decisions.

Key words: Chameleonic, Judiciary, Decision, Political and Matters

1. INTRODUCTION

The Judiciary, globally, is the arm of government saddled with the responsibility of resolving administrative cases and disputes arising between individuals and government, groups or legal persons. Situated within the tripartite arrangement in the doctrine of separation of powers which is germane in any democratic set up, the judiciary ought to act independently from the other two arms. This much was said in United States case of *O'Donoghue v. United States*¹.

If it be important to separate the several departments of government and restrict them to the exercise of their appointed powers, it follows, as a logical corollary, equally important, that each department should be kept completely independent of others – independent not in the sense that they shall not cooperate to the common end of carrying into effect the purpose of the constitution, but in the sense that the acts of each shall never be controlled by or subjected, directly and indirectly, to the coercive influence of the other departments.

The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria has provided for judicial powers under part 11 thereof². The judiciary and courts are more often than not used interchangeably as provided by the constitution³. The judicial powers of the federation shall be vested in the courts to which this section relates, being courts established for the federation. Equally, the judicial powers of a state shall be vested in the courts to which this section relates, being courts established subject as provided by this constitution, for a state.

The courts have developed established principles based on the age long principle of Judicial Precedent which guides them in arriving at decisions. These principles must be followed particularly when it relates to courts of subordinate jurisdiction and even with the Supreme Court, it is only when such a principle occasions injustice that the court can depart from its earlier decision which is akin to law.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The judiciary is most touted as the last hope of the common man. However, the judgments that are coming from the once hallowed institution, are gradually eroding this hope. The Nigerian judiciary is fast replacing the electorates in the determination of political office holders. This

1 *O'Donoghue v. United States* 77 Law Ed. US 1356.

2 Part II of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended.

3 Section 6(1) and (2) of the Constitution, *Ibid*.

is done for a price. According to Ojukwu⁴, corruption in the judiciary is indeed happening at an alarming rate. Like a wildfire, it has engulfed the rooftop already, and it is visible for everyone to see. Judges seem to no longer regard and uphold their judicial oath as it has merely been turned into a necessary ritual without much reverence for it. The problem that has triggered this research is that the consistency known in the “judicial parlance as judicial precedent” is fast eroding most especially in political matters.

2. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS

It is imperative to explain some concepts as maybe used in this work.

i. Judiciary

As stated earlier in this work, the doctrine of separation of powers has created three arms of government to wit; the Executive, Legislative and Judiciary. In the case of *Tony Anozia v. the Attorney General of Lagos State & 2 Ors*,⁸ the court of Appeal defined judiciary as follows:

The term “Judiciary” in essence, denotes the branch of government that is constitutionally responsible for interpreting the laws and administering justice. It is popularly known as the third arm of government. It is termed judicature, which denotes the act of judging or administering justice, by the application of the rule of law through duly constituted courts.

Those vested with the powers to preside in this hallowed office are judges. The primary duty of a judge is to ensure that no one suffers injustice and or is deprived of his liberty, freedom or denied his rights without remedy, following the due process of the law. The most important duty of the judiciary and indeed the judges include the power to hold the government or the elected members of the society accountable in law, for all their deeds. They are by their special training under duty to ensure that those who govern, be they elected by the people or not, act in accordance with the law⁹.

The power of judicial review of political issues is invested in the courts by virtue of the omnibus provisions of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and other relevant legislations.

4 Ojukwu Emmanuel “is the Judiciary Really the last Hope of a Common Man in Nigeria?” available at www.tekedia.com/isthejudiciary last accessed 3/6/2024.

8Ibid.

9Ibid.

ii. Political Matters

According to Abubakar, Election remains the most scientific method of leadership recruitment ever devised by man. It affords the opportunity for the people to select their leaders. Political parties therefore represent the only platforms through which politicians seeking election must stand on to win elections¹⁰.

In carrying out their constitutional duties, disputes more often than not arises. The judiciary then becomes the final arbiter to determine such disputes. The Constitution and the Electoral Act, have ample provisions for pre and post-election disputes¹¹. The challenge remains that these electoral disputes whether pre or post elections must be settled by courts. Unfortunately, the judiciary sings with discordant voices in giving their decisions in matters that have been since settled and principles established through the doctrine of judicial precedent. As such, there are conflicting judgments, coupled with unwanted and unmeritorious injunctions from courts of coordinate jurisdiction. In the case of the Supreme Court, the court has continued to shift its goal post in cases of similar facts which it has established and again giving decisions that are not founded on justice but on “Law”.

iii. Nigerian Judiciary and The Doctrine of Precedents

In Nigeria, the court system is organized in a hierarchical manner with the Supreme Court as the highest court in the land. The decision of the court is final and not appealable¹². It hears appeal from the Court of Appeal and exercises supervisory jurisdiction over subordinate courts. It sits in its original jurisdiction in few cases where there is a dispute between the component states and the federal government. Next to the apex court is the Court of Appeal¹³. It ranks second to the Supreme Court. It determines appeals from the High Courts and the Customary and Sharia Courts of Appeal. Its original jurisdiction is only to hear and determine any matter as to whether any one has been voted or elected to the position of President or Vice President of Nigeria.

10(2010) 15 NWLR (part 1216) 207 @ 237.

11Patrick Ocheja Okolo: “The Judiciary as a Vessel for The Advancement of the Economic, Social and Political Development of Nigeria” A Paper Presented at the Opening Ceremony of the Benue State Judiciary Legal Year 2016/2017 on 16/9/2017.

12 Section 230 CFRN 1999.

13 Section 229 CFRN 1999.

Lying beneath the Court of Appeal is the High Court either established by the federal government or by the states¹⁴. Also of coordinate jurisdiction in the hierarchy is the National Industrial Court with exclusive jurisdiction over trade disputes, labour practices, matters related to trade union disputes and compensation law¹⁵. There are also courts of inferior jurisdiction such as Magistrates, Customary and Sharia courts established by laws of respective states.

iv. The Doctrine of Judicial Precedent

According to Fyanka, Judicial precedent is defined as the making of law by a court in recognizing and applying new rules while administering justice. It refers to a decided case that furnishes a basis for determining later cases involving similar facts or issues. Again, judicial precedent is defined as a judgment or decision of a court of law cited as an authority for the legal principle embodied in the decision¹⁶.

The major doctrine used in the creation and development of case law or common law rules by the courts is the doctrine of judicial precedent whereby legal rules applicable to present or future litigation are found in prior cases known as precedents. This is elaborately captured thus¹⁷:

Judicial Precedent or case-law is, in our opinion, the clearest form of judicial law making. Simply put, it is the law laid down by courts in their judgments. The decision of Supreme Courts of law, are not only binding on the parties in the particular case, but is treated with respect and regarded as a statement of the law and as precedents which subsequent courts must follow whenever cases with same or similar facts and/or issues come before them.

According to Mohammed, the principle of judicial precedent mandates that within the hierarchy, the inferior court shall apply the principles decided by superior courts to similar facts before them, unless they are able to distinguish the facts of the cases before them from the facts

14 Section 249 CFRN 1999.

15Section 254A CFRN 1999.

16 Kaase Fyanka: *Nigeria Case Law method* (Kraft Books Limited, 2016) 381 quoted Garner, BA Black's Law Dictionary, 9th Edition (St. Pauls Mvesota: West Publishing, 2009) P. 1195.

17 Ibid Fyanka Kaase.

of the cases decided by the Superior Courts¹⁸. In *Adeyemi & Ors v. Achimu/NDIC (Assurance Bank Nigeria Ltd) & Ors*¹⁹ the Supreme Court explained the doctrine of stare decisis:

The principle of doctrine of “stare decisis” in our judicial jurisprudence, is a Latin phrase of a common law origin and it simply means “follow what has been decided” or “stand with what has been decided” as a cardinal principle in the administration of justice that like cases be decided alike, it is known that the facts of a case are very rarely, if at all, exactly the same with those of another case and so the principle does not require that facts of two (2) cases must be exactly the same before it applied. Infinitesimal, peripheral, inarticulate and minor differences in facts of two (2) cases do not hinder or prevent the application of the principle, as the determinant factor is that the facts of previous case are substantially and materially identical and similar to those of a latter case which calls for the application of the principle.

The purpose of judicial precedent is to serve as a guide in adjudication of cases by subordinate courts. In *Dingyadi v. INEC & Ors*²⁰ it was held that the meaning and import of judicial precedent is that where same points come again in litigation, it presupposes that the law has been solemnly declared in a previous case. It precludes the judges of subordinate courts from changing what has been determined. As was held in *Ardo v. Nyako & Ors*²¹. It was held that, the principle is designed to ensure orderliness, certainty and discipline in the judicial process.

Mohammed opines that the doctrine of judicial precedent or stare decisis does not only guide but also limits the discretion of subordinate courts with regards to all facts or circumstances over which the position of the law has already been decided or pronounced upon by those appellate superior courts²². To ensure certainty in the law, the discretion of subordinate courts is limited to only those facts and circumstances in respect of which there have not been decisions of superior appellate courts or those facts that can be distinguished from those over which such decisions have been made²³.

18 Abba B. Mohammed: “Judicial Precedent (Stare decisis); Stemming the Tide of Conflicting Judgments” being a paper presented on Wednesday 14th March, 2023 at a refresher Court for Judges and Kadis Held at the National Judicial Institution, Abuja from 13th – 17th of March, 2023.

19(2022) LPELR – 57069 (SC).

20 (2011)LPELR – 950 (SC).

21 (2014) LPELR – 22878 (SC).

22 Abba Mohammed Op Cit.

23 (2011) LPELR – 22878 (SC).

The Supreme Court respects its previous decisions and can only overrule itself where it considers that there are good and substantial reasons to do so such as where the decision is given *per incuriam*, on grounds of public policy, or where the retention of such a decision will perpetuate injustice²⁴.

The application of the principle of stare decisis and adherence to judicial precedence by the courts is one aspect of judicial policy which ensures consistency, certainty, reliability and orderliness in the development and application of legal rules/principles in the administration of justice. The use of the principle of judicial precedent is therefore, an indispensable tool in the determination of what the state of the law is at any given moment. It ensures a uniform treatment of similar cases, thus making judicial decision predictable²⁵.

3.1 Conflicting Decisions in Political Cases

Nigerian political experience since 1999 is very disturbing, as a requirement for leadership recruitments, the constitution requires that every person must be a member of a political party. He must contest and win elections in the percentage and spread as it may relate to such an election. The Independent National Electoral Commission is vested with the powers to issue guidelines to guide and guard political actors²⁶. In carrying out these duties, political parties end up in dispute either at pre-election or post-election matters. As a requirement of law, INEC has to as of necessity, be joined as a party. This is to make INEC bound by such decisions as may be arrived at by courts. Most often than not INEC is caught in the legal web of conflicting decisions putting them in dilemma of which one to follow since most of the decisions are from courts of coordinate jurisdiction.

The Supreme Court on the other hand is guilty of overruling itself in decisions they have taken in no distant time thereby creating uncertainty in the judicial space. INEC Chairman Mahmood expressed his worry in this manner, “it appears that in a number of electoral cases in Nigeria today, the settled law is now unsettled and the time honoured principle of certain decisions does not seem to matter anymore”.

24 See the Supreme Court cases of *Associated Discount House V. Almagamated Trustees* (No. 2) SC. Per Ogbuagwu JSC and *Veepee Industries Limited V. Cocoa Industries Limited* (2008) LPELR – 346161.

25 Mohammed Op Cit Quoted the dictum of Garba JSC in *Adeyemi & Ors. V. Achimu NDIC/Assurance Bank Nigeria Ltd. & Ors* and Kekere Ekun JSC in *State V. Yanga* (2021) LPELR – 53068 (SC).

26 Section 2 Electoral Act, 2022 and Section 15 Part 1 of the Third Schedule of the Constitution of Nigeria 1999 as amended.

The Court of Appeal in some cases dismissed the use of a particular colour of biro for accreditation of voters other than the one prescribed in the manual for conduct of election as inconsequential. But the court of Appeal in the case of *Fayemi V. Oni*²⁷ nullified the Ekiti State Governorship elections in 63 out of the 177 wards in Ekiti State just because accreditation was done with a red biro instead of blue stipulated by the manual for the conduct of election. The Court of Appeal in this judgment also shifted the burden of proof for non-accreditation from the petitioner to the respondent. This, no doubt contravenes the time tested principle that he who assert must prove.

In *Amosun V. Daniel*,²⁸ Ogun State Governorship Election Petition, the court of Appeal held that one Tunde Yadeke was not an expert in the examination and analysis of electoral materials. But in the *Aregbesola Vs. Oyinlola*²⁹ Osun State Governorship Election Petition, the Court of Appeal ruled that Tunde Yadeke was an expert. These are two cases with similar facts but on which different judgments were delivered. The irony is that some members featured in the panels of the court in both cases.

To further illustrate the conflicting nature of judgments of the Court of Appeal. One of the conflicts is on whether or not witness statement on Oath must include the exact words used in the first schedule of the Oath Act. In *Obumneke V. Sylvester*³⁰ the issue for determination was whether the petition was incompetent in view of the fact that the petitioner failed to use the exact words used by the legislature in the first schedule to the Oaths Act, 2004, in concluding his statement on Oath.

The Court of Appeal held that failure to use the exact words or format prescribed by the legislature in the 1st schedule to the Oath Act in concluding the statements on oath is fatal and rendered the statements inadmissible.

However, the Court of Appeal on the same issue in *Ibrahim V. INEC*³¹ held thus:-

The clear intention of the legislature under the Oath titled 'Statutory Declaration' is to afford persons who intend to make declaration such as marriage, age or assets to subscribe to that declaration. It is not the intention of the legislature that the wording of the affidavit to render it valid non-compliance is not fatal to petition.

27 (2010) 17NWLR (pt. 1222) 543.

28 (2009) JELR 43201 (Court of Appeal).

29 (2009) 14 NWLR (pt. 1162) 429.

30 (2010) All FWLR (pt. 506) 195.

31 (2007) Election Petitions Report 50.

*Onwuka Nkeiruka V. Dimobi Joseph*³² is another judgment of the Court of Appeal that conflicts with *Ibrahim v. INEC*³³ concerning the application of the Oath Act to a Statement on Oath. The Court of Appeal, Enugu Division held that non-compliance of written statement on Oath with provisions of section 13 of the Oath Act and paragraph 1(1) (b) of the Practice Direction 2007 is fatal to an election petition (Jurisdictional matter). It must be noted that these witnesses must be sworn on oath before the court, before adopting their witness statement on Oath. So what really is the intention of the legislature? despite all the above, the clear and unambiguous provision of paragraph 41(1) of the Electoral Act 2010 as amended states thus³⁴:

“41(1) subject to any statutory provision or any provision of these paragraphs relating to evidence, any fact required to be proved at the hearing of a petition shall be proved by written depositions and oral examination of witnesses in open court.”

41(2) Documents which parties consented to at the pre-hearing session or rather exhibits shall be tendered from the bar or by the party where he is not represented by legal practitioner.

41(3) There shall be no oral examination of a witness during evidence-in-chief except to lead the witness to adopt his written deposition and tendered in evidence all disputed documents or other exhibits referred to in the deposition.

(8) Some with leave of the Tribunal or Court, no document, plan, photograph or model shall be received in evidence at the hearing of a petition unless it has been listed or filed along with the petition in the case of the petitioner or filed along with reply in the case of the respondent.

The provision of paragraph 41(1) quoted above, did not use the word “Oath” to describe witness written deposition. Should the practice direction override this? Practice Direction is to assist the court in doing justice. See the provisions of paragraph 53(1) of the Electoral Act 2010 as amended which states thus:

Non-compliance with any of the provisions of this schedule or with a rule of practice for the time being operative, except otherwise stated or implied, shall not render any proceeding void, unless the Tribunal or Court so directs, but the proceedings may be set aside wholly or in part as irregular, or amended, or otherwise dealt with in such manner and on such terms as the Tribunal or Court may deem fit and just.

32 (2009).

33 *Ibrahim v. INEC* Op Cit.

34 Section 41(1) Electoral Act, 2010 as amended.

The provisions of paragraph 41(1) of Electoral Act 2010 does not support that finding but before adoption, the witness deposition could be said to be so. But after its adoption in open court and it is unchallenged or not discredited under cross-examination and no opposing deposition on the other side as to grant the court a discretion as to which to believe, the court must act on it as credible and unchallenged evidence before it.

In the Presidential Election Petition – *CPC (Congress for Progressive change) V. INEC & Others*³⁵, the Court of Appeal Abuja Division held thus:

“That witness statements on Oath are mere depositions.”

In *CPC V. INEC & Ors.*, the Court of Appeal held original (duplicate) copy of election results in Forms EC series are primary evidence requiring no certificate for its admissibility, but turned around to reject the same set of documents from about 24 states including the report of the petitioner analysing the results shown on these Form EC series on the ground that the witness had no personal knowledge of the documents. Even when the documents were all adjudged relevant and in issue in the same ruling (having admitted same from Anambra State). The provisions of paragraph 41(8) of the Electoral Act 2010 (as amended) quoted above is clear once it has been complied with, no reason should be advanced to reject any exhibit in Electoral matters. The only recourse left to the court is the weight to be attached.

In fact, in the course of hearing the same petition, a petitioner’s witness tendered photocopy of his own handwritten petition to INEC, with copy sent to and receive at State Security Services Office in Owerri, Imo State. INEC did not deny the existence of the letter, notice to produce was issued and served. The letter was pleaded and listed amongst the list of documents. The letter was a complaint raised on the day of the election against the conduct of the election held on the same day. The court rejected it on ground that it was a photocopy. Is that not technicality?

In recent times the courts in the build up to the primary elections in Edo State issued conflicting judgment against and in favour of governor Obaseki. While the Federal High Court sitting in Port Harcourt barred him from participating in the primaries, the High Court of Edo State sitting at Ekpoma cleared him³⁶.

In 2016, the Governorship tussle between Okezie Ikpeazu and his main contender, Uchechukwu Ogah demonstrated this ugly trend in the judiciary. Litigation concerning the

35 (2012) NWLR (pt. 1280) 106.

36Mamman Mike Osuman: “Conflicting Orders and Decisions of Courts on Political Matters” available at www.guardian.ng/features/law accessed 11/12/2023.

party primaries in the state saw the different court judgments from Federal High Court in Abuja and Osisioma in Abia State as well as Owerri in Imo State. Justice Okon Abang of the Federal High Court in Abuja (as he then was) ordered the Governor to vacate his seat and directed INEC to issue a certificate of return to Ogah who came second in that party primaries of 8th December, 2014. The governor obtained an *ex parte* injunction restraining his opponent from being sworn in from the state High Court sitting at Osisioma³⁷.

In the leadership tussle of the chairmanship of PDP involving Senator Modu Sherrif, the Federal High Court in Abuja and Lagos recognized Sherrif as the Chairman of the party. Another Federal High Court in Port-Harcourt recognized Makarfi³⁸. The situation got so embarrassing that the Chief Justice of Nigeria had to summon six heads of courts in the states. In one week, three courts in different states issued counter orders about the office of the national chairman of the Peoples Democratic Party. On the 24th August, 2021, Rivers State High Court sitting in Port-Harcourt restrained Uche Secondus from parading himself as the National Chairman of the PDP. In a dramatic twist, the Kebbi State High Court in Birnin Kebbi restored Secondus as National Chairman of the party on 27th August, 2021. A day after Mr. Secondus' reinstatement, another High Court in Calabar, Cross River State issued an interim order restraining him from assuming office. This angered the then Chief Justice of Nigeria to warn the state Chief Judges to stop the nonsense³⁹.

The Supreme Court has not fared better. It has Shifted back and forth. The Supreme Court in a number of cases including *Esenowo v. Ukpong*⁴⁰ held that even the way you write your name can make you someone else. This principle was upheld in *PDP v. Degi-Eremienyo*⁴¹ where the Supreme Court nullified the win of David Lyon as Governor Elect of Bayelsa State as his Deputy-Elect was using multiple names which is suggestive of fraud. This decision was quickly overruled in the case of *Dantiye v. APC*⁴². The court in *David Edevbie v. Oborevwo Sherrif Francis Orowhedor*⁴³ held:

37The Blue Print: "How Conflicting Court Orders, Rulings Fuel PDP Crisis" available at www.blueprinting/how/conflicting-court-orders accessed 12/12/2023.

38 Ibid.

39 Premium Time, "Conflicting Court Orders: Stop this Nonsense, CJN Warns Judges" available at www.premiumtimesng.com/headlinesz accessed 13/12/2023.

40 (1999) 6 NWLR (pt. 608) 611.

41 (2021) 9 NWLR (pt.1781) 274.

42 ((2021) 19 NWLR (pt. 1808) see also Elegbeke & Ors (2022) 20 NWLR (pt. 1837).

43 Urep. SC/CV/1132/2022 delivered on 21st October, 2022.

The suggestions by the appellant's counsel that the decision in these cases are not good law presumably because it does not support their appellant's stance is quite disheartening, even with the clear pronouncement made by this court in APC v. Elegbeke that the decision in Dantiye v. APC supersedes/overrule the earlier decision of this court in PDP v. Degi-Eremienyo⁴⁴.

This decision is unfortunate because the decision in Degi-Eremienyo nullifying the win of APC in Bayelsa was not a year old when the Supreme Court decided to shift from that position thereby denying the people the leadership they selected. In another unfortunate decision, the Supreme Court held that party congresses made prior to the election constitute pre-election matter. This decision was quickly overturned in *APC v. Moses*⁴⁵ where the court reversed itself from this position.

The Supreme Court has moved back and forth on issues of using originating summons to commence pre-election matter. The Federal High Court pre-election practice direction requires all pre-election matters be commenced by originating summons⁴⁶. In the case of All Progressives Congress and Bashir Machina, which originated from the Yobe State High Court where Machina's name was substituted and in its place Lawan was submitted to INEC. Machina then commenced an action using originating summons wherein he alleged that APC "fraudulently" substituted his name with the name of Senator Lawan. The Apex Court in a majority decision held that since Machina's allegation was based on fraud against APC and Lawan, he ought to have initiated the action via writ of summons instead of originating summons⁴⁷. This is contrary to the time honoured principle of the court as settled in *Aguma v. APC*⁴⁸ where the Supreme Court held that where a statute or rule of court prescribes a condition precedent to the assumption of jurisdiction, the condition precedent must be fulfilled. In *Gusau v. Lawal*⁴⁹ where the court held that where a statute prescribes a mode for doing an act, that and no other shall be accepted. A commentator on this case said⁵⁰:

44 All Cases Mentioned in the quotation are referred in footnote 40 and 41.

45 (2021) NWLR (pt. 1796) 272.

46 See Rule IV of the Federal High Court Pre-Election Practice Directions, 2022 which provides that every pre-election matter shall be commenced by originating summons as specified in forms 1, 4 or 5 of Appendix 6 to the Federal High Court (Civil Procedure) Rules.

47 The Guardian, "Dissecting the Supreme Court in Lawan v. Machina" available at www.guardian.ng/opinion/desscting accessed 13/12/2023.

48 (2021) 14 NWLR (pt.1796) 351.

49 (2023) LPELR – 60152 (SC).

50 The Guardian Op Cit.

Sadly, the inconsistencies demonstrated by the Nigerian Courts in recent times have been so consistent that they significantly diminish public trust in the dignity and integrity of the judiciary as presently constituted.

This sad development was commented upon by Yemi Osinbajo thus⁵¹:

Clearly the legal process loses its credibility where it is uncertain in its outcome even in the case of clear precedent. The judicial process is being rapidly – even laymen now wonder how come the same court cannot give consistent rulings.

3. THE CHAMELEONIC NATURE OR DIFFERENTIAL OF JUDGMENTS IN POLITICAL MATTERS

Judicial precedent is the science of law that provides fixed principles that forms the basis of subsequent judicial decisions. Courts of law particularly in subordinate jurisdiction must, as a matter of course, follow such principles. These principles become settled and known to actors within the judicial circle and the public at large. In political matters, Nigerian courts have dumped these settled principles and give decisions dialectical to each other on same principles. This makes these judgments chameleonic in nature which calls for concern.

4. THE NATURE AND CHARACTER OF APPOINTMENTS

According to Ikoni⁵² persons selected for judicial office shall be individuals of integrity and ability with appropriate training or qualifications in law. Any method of judicial selection shall safeguard against judicial appointments for improper motives. In the selection of judges, there shall be no discrimination against a person on the grounds of tribe, sex, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or status, except a requirement that a candidate for judicial office must be a national of the country concerned, shall not be considered discriminatory. The ways in which judges are appointed and subsequently promoted are crucial to the independence of the judiciary. Thus, when appointment of men and women to the bench is premised on extraneous considerations such as god-fatherism, political connections, religious leanings, “federal character” (without any regard for merit and competence) and

51 E.Q. Okolie, “A Critical Review of Conflicting Judgments of Appellate Courts in Election Matters” available at www.globalacademicgroup.com accessed 13/12/2023.

52U.D. Ikoni, “Demystifying the Autonomy Challenges of the Judiciary” Being a paper presented at the symposium, organized by the Benue State Judiciary to mark the 2018/2019 Legal Year on 15/9/2018. P. 16-17.

monetary inducements, the ultimate victim is justice. The society is bound to suffer and bear the brunt of the consequences of having incompetent judges on the Bench.

Akpata exclaimed that when he was the president of Nigerian Bar Association, he found out that there is a deliberate attempt by the political class to capture the judiciary and that has very grave implication on the rule of law. He said⁵³

I sat on the appointment committee for the appointment of judges. And what I saw was bizarre. That a good judge will emerge out of Nigeria, out of that process, is by fluke only, sheer luck, luck of the draw, we play Russian roulette with judiciary appointments in Nigeria.

Lekan went ahead to quote the outbursts of a politician over court judgments, he said

We have gone to the Court of Appeal and the final destination is the Supreme Court (of Nigeria) and we will meet there and that is when they know who we know and we will know who they know⁵⁴

Dania writing about appointment of children of judicial officers on the Bench Quoted Prof. Itse Sagay where he said “sons and daughters of retired and serving judges and justices are being dominated into sensitive judicial positions at the expense of more qualified candidates without privilege support and backing”. He said this favouritism is a pathway to future judicial malfeasance and miscarriage of justice.⁵⁵

From the discussion above, it is clear to decipher the differentiation arising from contradictory judgments and the changing faces of our judges. This is no doubt the albatross on the neck of the Nigerian Judiciary. No wonder established principles no longer matter, the capture of the judiciary by the political class is the foundation of all these evil.

5. RECOMMENDATION

It is not in doubt that the judiciary by its nature is revered by people and has for itself standards which drives its consistency. This is known as precedence. This guides the court in subsequent decisions even if the venue or Coram of the court is different. This no doubt evokes the

53Lekan Sote, “State Capture of Judiciary” available at www.thepunch.ng/state-capitory/voted accessed 13/12/2023

54Ibid Olu Akpata a former NBA president.

55Onozure Dania, “Judiciary Appointments must be Merit based, not Family Affiliation-Lawyers” available at www.punch.ng.com/judiciary-appointments accessed 23/12/23.

confidence of the public in its decisions. Where this is absent, it brings the entire institution to ridicule. Kperogi wrote⁵;

When a court dismissed a previous case as incompetent because it was pre-election matter when it was filed by one party but accepts it as the basis for overturning the votes of hundreds of thousands of citizens when it was filed by another party, you don't need to be smart to know that something is wrong.

The major contributory factors are corruption that is endemic in political matters and the nature of appointments into the bench of the Nigeria judiciary. It is recommended that;

- ii. The judiciary should do an in-house cleansing to rid itself of corrupt judges.
- iii. There should be a constitutional court to handle electoral matters at the exclusion of other courts. The judges there should be permanent not adhoc as is presently the case in Election Tribunals.
- iv. The appointments into the courts should be strictly based on merit and not on filial basis.
- v. The disciplinary measures against the judges should be housed outside the judiciary to avoid confraternity.

6. CONCLUSION

The inconsistencies in the judgments and orders from our courts have assumed a worrisome dimension as the system is gradually descending towards a total collapse. The reason for this is calculated from the view point that the independence of the judiciary has eroded. Most fundamental is the process of judicial recruitment which is faulty. The trend now is that the judges are recruited from family circles. Most of the judges do not merit to sit on the bench. Most importantly, the politicians have surrounded the institution and have judges at their beck and call. It is safe to conclude that; if nothing urgent is done, the judiciary is at imminent risk of collapse.

⁵ Farooq A. Kperogi. "Nigerian Judiciary as lost Hype of Justice" available@farroqkperogi.com last accessed 3/5/2024.